

Fluctuations in Generalized Statistical Mechanics

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In regular statistical mechanics, “ln” of the grand canonical partition function is applied to bosons and fermions. In addition, the grand canonical partition function, which is a weighted sum of partition functions of different N’s, is used to calculate a measure of fluctuations: $\langle N^2 \rangle - \langle N \rangle^2$. This value is said to be sharply peaked at N_{ave} with a width of $\sqrt{N_{ave}}$ (1). Furthermore in (1), it is noted that Helmholtz free energy $F(N_{ave}, V, T) = N_{ave} z - kT \ln(\text{grand partition function})$. (Here $z = \exp(u/T)$ where u is the chemical potential). For generalized statistical mechanics, $\ln[g(f)] = -(e-u)/T$, where g comes from the “physics” (e.g for fermions $g = f/(1-f)$ and for bosons $f/(1+f)$). Kaniadakis (2) gives a recipe for calculating entropy density, namely: $\int df \ln(g(f))$. Thus, using $E - TS + uN$ one may obtain: $-T \ln(\text{grand partition function})$ and calculate $\langle N^2 \rangle - \langle N \rangle^2 = z \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} \ln(\text{Grand partition function})$.

In this note, however, we wish to consider $\ln[g(f)] = -(e-u)/T$ as arising purely from a time reversal elastic scattering balance. In such a case, one does not need to define entropy or a partition function. We try, albeit in a hand-way manner, to investigate first order fluctuations based only on scattering considerations.

Scattering Approach

In a number of notes, we have argued one may find the equilibrium number distribution $f((e-u)/T)$ strictly from elastic scattering considerations with no need for entropy or partition function calculations. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, one uses $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and takes \ln of the former and equates to the latter multiplied by $1/T$ with u/T added in. For fermions and bosons, one uses $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)[1 - f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 - f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1 - f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1 - f(e_2)]$ and takes the \ln of the latter equating to the former with u/T added in and e divided by T . Kaniadakis (2) argues that for general scattering, one has:

$\ln(k(f)) = -(e-u)/T$ ((1)). For the MB case, k = the identity function, for fermions $g = f/(1-f)$ and for bosons $g = f/(1+f)$.

Using ((1)), one may obtain the number of particles with energy e , so there seems to be no need to introduce the idea of entropy and then use it to obtain a grand canonical partition function. Density fluctuations in statistical mechanics, however, seem to usually be obtained by taking various derivatives of the \ln of the grand canonical partition function. The grand canonical partition function is a weighted sum of canonical partition functions each representing a different overall particle number N , so one may find the spread in N . If one only uses a scattering approach, there is no grand canonical partition function and it seems one is led to other considerations for fluctuations.

Fluctuations in the Grand Canonical Partition Function

Kaniadakis (2) defines an entropy density: $S_d = \int df \ln(g(f))$ ((2)) such that:

$d/df S_d + d/df (e-u)/T f = 0$ ((3)), but $d/df S_d = \ln(g(f))$, so Kaniadakis entropy is created by

integrating over df to “cancel” d/df in the variation. A main feature $S = \int S_d d \text{ phase space}$ is that $E - TS + uN$ yields $-kT \ln(\text{grand partition function})$. One may test this for fermions for example, where $\ln(g(f)) = (e-u)/T$ and $g(f) = f/(1-f)$. Then, $S_d = E - uN + \ln(1 - \exp(-(e-u)/T))$. (1) page 186.

Given that one obtains the grand canonical partition function from the Kaniadakis entropy, one may consider density fluctuations (1):

$$\langle N^2 \rangle - \langle N \rangle^2 = z \frac{d}{dz} z \frac{d}{dz} \ln(\text{Grand partition function}) \quad ((3))$$

In (1), it is shown that ((3)) equals $N_{ave} kT / (v) \frac{1}{v} (-dP/d(v))$ where $v = V/N$.

The interpretation seems to follow from:

Grand Partition function = $\sum_N z^N Q(N)$ ((4)) where $Q(N)$ = the canonical partition function for N particles.

Fluctuations in a Scattering Scheme

If one only makes use of time reversal elastic scattering balance, it seems one does not need to make use of entropy or the grand canonical partition function. Yet, fluctuations still occur and one needs to find a way of describing them. We attempt to develop a first order scheme.

Before doing so, however, consider the following simple, hand-wavy scheme. Imagine one has a gas with only four allowable energies and two allowable reactions $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ (i.e. the forward and backward reactions). Imagine one has 5 particles of e_1 and 3 of e_2 and 4 of e_3 and 4 of e_4 . (Thus, $e_3 = e_4$.) The forward and backward rates for a reaction are the same (or can be made so if one tweaks the numbers slightly i.e. $5 \cdot 3 = 15$ and $4 \cdot 4 = 16$). There are only 3 e_2 's which may interact with 5 e_1 's, while there are 4 e_3 's and 4 e_4 's. The rate for an e_1 - e_2 reaction is the same as for an e_3 - e_4 reaction. Thus, it seems that in a tiny time interval, 3 e_2 's will react with 3 e_1 's, leaving 2 e_1 's alone. Thus, one loses 3 e_1 's and 3 e_2 's. In this same time, 3 reactions may occur between e_3 and e_4 (rate balance). Thus, 1 e_3 and 1 e_4 will not interact, but 3 of each will create 3 new e_1 's and 3 e_2 's in this time period. Thus, there is a balance. To calculate fluctuations, one may consider the probability that an e_1 - e_2 reaction occurs, but its counterpart e_3 - e_4 does not, or vice versa.

Let us consider fluctuations, but taking a tiny time dt such that only one reaction has the probability to occur. A reaction occurs with the probability $g(e_1)g(e_2) = G(e_1 + e_2) = G(E)$. The reverse reaction has the same probability. Note: $g(e_1) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$. Then, e_1 and e_2 may

react or not react and the same applies for e3 and e4 so there are 4 combinations with probabilities:

- A) GG (both (e1-e2) and (e3-e4) reactions leading to a number balance)
- B) G(1-G) (e1 reacts, e3 does not, leading to an imbalance)
- C) (1-G)G (e1 does not react, e3 does, leading to an imbalance)
- D) (1-G)(1-G) (no reactions, so a number balance)

Adding: $GG + G(1-G) + (1-G)G + (1-G)(1-G) = 1$. $G(1-G)$ leads to a loss of e1, while $(1-G)G$ to a gain. On average, there is no change, but this seems to be similar to tossing a coin, but with the added scenario that one does not toss it during all time intervals dt because for GG and $(1-G)(1-G)$ of the time, there is no fluctuation. As an approximation, consider GG close to 0, then:

$1-2G$ is the probability of no fluctuation (i.e. no e1 and e3 reaction or both react)
 G is the probability of a +1 fluctuation and G is the probability of -1 fluctuation.

Note: This fluctuation depends only on scattering. Consider the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which $g(f)=f$. Then $G=f(e1)f(e2)$. For the example above, there were 5 particles with e1, 3 with e2. $3*5=15$ while $4*4$ (for e3 and e4) =16. Technically, the two numbers should be the same, but this is an approximation. Then $G=15/16^2$ or roughly $1/16$. In general, for the MB case, $G=f(e1)f(e2) = \exp(-e1/T) / [\exp(-e1/T) + \exp(-e2/T) + \exp(-e3/T) + \exp(-e4/T)]^2$. For generalized statistics, the same formula holds, but $G=g(e1)g(e2)$ with $g(e1)=\exp(-e1/T)$ or $g(e1)= \exp(-e1/T) / [\exp(-e1/T) + \exp(-e2/T) + \exp(-e3/T) + \exp(-e4/T)]$ in this simple example.

Thus, for $[(1-G)(1-G) + GG] *100\%$ of the time or $(225/256 + 16/256)*100\%$ of the time, one would not see any fluctuations in equilibrium numbers. For roughly $1/8$ of the time, however, there would be fluctuations. For roughly $1/16$ of the time, there would be fluctuations of $GGN(e1)= 5 (1/16)$ above the equilibrium value of $N(e1)$ or roughly $5.33 e1$ particles and for $1/16$ of the time, there would be $5-5/16$ or $4.67 e1$ particles in the crude example given above.

The example above considers only one channel open to e1, namely a reaction with e2. Imagine all channels are open and apply the above. For each reaction, there are still the options: GG (1-G)(1-G) G(1-G) and (1-G)G which are normalized. Each reaction, however, comes with a weight $\exp(-ej/T) / C$ where $C = \text{Sum over } i \exp(-ei/T)$. If the Sum is replaced with an integral over phase space, the normalization is: $C= x^3 / V$ where $x=\text{sqrt}[6.28 hbar^2/ (mKT)]$ (2). The probability for an e1 particle to react in any channel seems to be $f(e1)$ so $(1-f(e1))$ is the probability it does not react.

Probability of no change in the e1 equilibrium number=

Sum over ej $g(ej) [g(ej)g(e1)]^2$ (similar to GG) +
 Sum over ej $g(ej) [1-g(ej)g(e1)]^2$ (similar to (1-G)(1-G)).

To a first approx, this is: $\sum_{e_j} g(e_j)[1-2g(e_j)g(e_1)] = 1-2g(e_1)$ because $g(e_j)$ is normalized.

Thus, approximately $(1-2g(e_1))*100\%$ of the time, there is no change in the equilibrium number of e_1 , namely $f(e_1)$. ((5))

Approximate Probability for a change of +1 per reaction = $\sum_{e_j} g(e_j) g(e_j)g(e_1) [1-g(e_j)g(e_1)]$ approx equals $\sum_{e_j} g(e_j) g(e_j) g(e_1) = B$ ((6a))

$g(e_j)*g(e_j) = C*C \exp(-2e_j/T)$ where the sum over e_j may be replaced with a phase space integral. The integral is like the usual normalization one with T replaced by $T/2$. Thus:

$$\text{Integral dphase space } g(e_j)g(e_j) = \{ V / [\sqrt{6.28 \hbar^2 / mk \cdot 5T}]^3 \}^* \{ [\sqrt{6.28 \hbar^2 / mkT}]^3 / V \}^2$$

So $B = g(e_1) 1/(2.8V) [\sqrt{6.28 \hbar^2 / mkT}]^3$ This approx only holds for small $g(e_1)$.

Or $B = \exp(-e_1/T) 1/(2.8V^2) [\sqrt{6.28 \hbar^2 / mkT}]^6$ ((6b)) Here V is the volume.

Approximate Probability for a change of -1 per reaction also approx = B

Thus, $B*100\%$ of the time one has an increase of $B*f(e_1)$ from the equilibrium number $f(e_1)$ and $B*100\%$ of the time a decrease of $B*f(e_1)$ below $f(e_1)$. ((7)) For $(1-2g(e_1))*100\%$ of the time one has no fluctuation.

These are approximate numbers as $B < g(e_1)$ so the three probabilities add up to: $1-2g(e_1)+\{2g(e_1) \sum_i g(e_i)g(e_i)\}$ which is less than 1 because a number of terms have been dropped. One may retain extra terms to obtain a better estimate.

(Note: For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case $f(e_1)$ is a probability and needs to be multiplied by N , but for fermions and bosons $f(e_1)$ is a count of particles with e_1 .)

Fluctuation Distribution

It seems the probability for a decrease in e_1 particles is B and for an increase also B . Instead of calculating only extremes $f(e_i)B$ above $f(e_i)$ or $f(e_i)B$ below $f(e_i)$ as done above, one may try to find a distribution of first order fluctuations.

Let m_1 be the number of losses of e_1 and $f(e_1)B-m_1$, the gains. $f(e_1)-Bf(e_1) - 2m_1$ e_1 particles do not change. Here there are $f(e_1)$ particles at different locations in the volume V and so each e_1 particle is identified by its position. Thus, at $r(a)$, an e_1 particle may not react (while an e_3 and e_4 do creating an extra e_1), while at $r(b)$, an e_1 particle may react, disappearing, but an e_3 and e_4 may not react to compensate.

Probability of $(f(e_1)B-2m_1)$ changes = $C_1 \{f(e_1)! / [Bf(e_1)! (f(e_1)-Bf(e_1))!]\} \{Bf(e_1)! / [m_1! (f(e_1)B-m_1)!]\} * B^{Bf(e_1)}$ where $m_1 \max = f(e_1)B$ and $m_1 \min = 0$ ((8a))

If one only considers e_1 and ignores all other energies then:

Probability of $(f(e_1)B-2m_1)$ changes = $C_2 / [m_1! (f(e_1)B-m_1)!]$ ((8b))

Thus, the “arrangements” in space discussed above do not come into play if one only considers a distribution for e_1 , but would come into play if one were comparing energies e_1 and e_2 for etc. Thus, ((8a)) is more general. This is interesting because $f(e_i)$ may be found by only considering scattering. This scattering maps into a picture of chains with reactions in different locations on the chain. Thus, a scattering picture which requires no entropy considerations to obtain $f(e_i)$ maps into an “arrangement” picture which involves entropy. When calculating fluctuations, however, entropy or arrangement considerations seem to be important.

For $(1-2g(e_1))*100\%$ of the time one has no fluctuation, while for $2*B*100\%$ of the time there are fluctuations with a distribution given by ((8a)) and a range extending from $B*f(e_1)$ above and below $f(e_1)$.

If $f(e_1)B-m_1$ is very large and m_1 is large, one may use Stirling’s approximation for ((8b)) even though B is small. Then:

Probability of $(f(e_1)B-2m_1)$ changes = $C_2 \exp(-m_1 \ln(m_1)) \exp[-(Bf-m_1)\ln(Bf-m_1)]$

One may extremize the probability by variation and find:

$m_1 = Bf/2$ which means no fluctuation. Nevertheless, there are probabilities for fluctuations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in previous notes that an equilibrium number distribution $f(e_i)$ may be obtained solely from elastic scattering criteria, namely $g(f) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ where u is the chemical potential (normalization factor). The function g depends on kinematics. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case it is the identity function, but for bosons and fermions $g = f/(1+f)$ and $f/(1-f)$. Kaniadakis has defined an entropy density $S_d = \int df \ln(g(f))$. Using $S = \int d\text{phase space } S_d$, one may equate $E - TS + uN$ with $-kT \ln(\text{Grand partition function})$. The grand partition function may then be used to calculate density fluctuations $\langle N^2 \rangle - \langle N \rangle^2$. In the pure scattering scenario, however, there is no grand partition function which begs the question: How does one describe fluctuations? In the above we try to present a crude method to obtain first order fluctuations. We argue:

A) $(1-2g(e_1))^*100\%$ of the time there are no fluctuations $g(e_1)= C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where C is a normalization constraint given above

B) $2*B*100\%$ of the time there is a fluctuation between $f(e_1)*B$ above and below $f(e_1)$ where $B= g(e_1) 8/V [\text{sqrt}(6.28 \text{ hbar}^2/ m kT)]^3$ with a distribution given by:

$$\text{Probability of } (f(e_1)B-2m_1 \text{ changes}) = C2/ [m_1! (f(e_1)B-m_1)!]$$

where $m_1 \text{ max} = Bf$ and $m_1 \text{ min}=0$.

$f(e_i)$ may be found by only considering scattering. The scattering approach maps into a picture of chains with reactions in different locations on the chain. Thus, a scattering picture which requires no entropy considerations to obtain $f(e_i)$ maps into an "arrangement" picture which involves entropy. When calculating fluctuations, however, entropy or arrangement considerations seem to be important.

These are approximate values which depend on $g(e_1)$ being small, say below .25.

References

- 1.Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987)
- 2.Kaniadakis, G. Nonlinear Kinematics Underlying General Statistics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467.pdf>